

Electrochemical Behaviour of Synthetic Humic Acids

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Synthetic humic acids have been prepared from each of glucose, catechol and hydroquinone with or without amino acids as the source of nitrogen. The humus formed was separated by alkali solution by centrifugation from which humic acids were precipitated by hydrochloric acid at pH 2-3. They were purified by repeating the processes of dissolution and precipitation and finally by dialysis and electro-dialysis. Conductometric and potentiometric studies of the solutions of the synthetic humic acids reveal their polyelectrolytic nature.

THE behaviour of polymeric electrolytes in solution is largely determined by the electrostatic free energy arising from the dissociation of the ionogenic groups from the polymer backbone. Conductometry and potentiometry are the two well known methods employed for identification as well as determination of the amount and under suitable conditions, the relative orientation of these ionogenic groups in a polyfunctional macromolecule. Though considerable amount of work has been done on the electrochemical properties of soil humic acids, showing that they contain carboxyl, hydroxyl (both phenolic and alcoholic), enolic and primary amino and imino groups, very little study appears to have been made on their synthetic counterparts. The work presented here aims at obtaining information of the conductometric and potentiometric behaviours of synthetic humic acids and comparing the results with known observations in this field on the naturally occurring soil humic acids. Van Dijk¹ reported conductometric curves for humic acid (both synthetic and natural) in dimethyl formamide medium with sodium isopropylate as the titrant. The maximum observed in the curve corresponds to the equivalence point for the weak acid groups, presumably carboxyl, while the minimum which is less reproducible, is assumed to correspond to still weaker acidic groups, namely, the phenolic hydroxyls. Sprengel² and Oden³ treated soil humic acids as true acids, whereas Bauman and Gully⁴ considered them as colloidal acids. Rindell⁵ noted in humic acid solutions the characteristics of both the colloidal and true acids. Thiele and Kettner⁶ failed to obtain smooth potentiometric titration curves, the titrations being carried out discontinuously to ensure equilibrium. Various authors⁷⁻¹³ have given titration curves of natural humic acids in aqueous media. Zadmar¹⁴ showed

the base exchange capacity calculated at pH 7.0 to be in the order :

A similar conclusion was arrived at by Chatterjee and Basu¹⁵. Marshall and Patnaik¹² reported measurement of cation binding by different fractions of soil humic acid, and observed a close similarity between humic and hymatomelanin acid fractions.

Several investigators tried to determine the amount of carboxyl groups by potentiometry assuming that phenolic hydroxyls are titrated above pH 7.0 while the carboxyl groups are neutralised upto pH 7.0. Others consider pH 8.2 as the limit instead of pH 7.0. However, Van Dijk¹ pointed out that when applying this to a titration curve of humic acids, the content of phenolic hydroxyl groups would be a function of concentration of the humic acid solution, more acid groups being dissociated at a certain pH as the solution is diluted.

Materials and Methods

Humic acids were prepared from phenols according to the method of Coulson, Davies and Khan¹⁶ and from glucose following Berthelot's¹⁷ method. The methods are briefly described below.

Glucose Humic Acid (GL-H) : Glucose (35 g) was dissolved in about 200 ml of 9-10% HCl and the solution was refluxed intermittently for 28 hr on a boiling water bath. After cooling the material in the flask was centrifuged, and the residue dissolved by adding sodium hydroxide solution (pH 9.0) and again centrifuged. The supernatant liquid was brought to pH 2-3 with HCl. The precipitate obtained was separated and dissolved in alkali followed by precipitation with HCl. These operations were repeated thrice, and finally the humic acid was washed several times with 0.1 N HCl and freed from electrolytes by dialysis followed by electro-dialysis.

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Catechol Humic Acids (CT-H and CA-H): Catechol (1.5 gm) and glycine, leucine, histidine, alanine and glutamic acid (each 0.3 gm) were dissolved in warm 0.1 N alkali, $K_2S_2O_8$ (2.8 gm) was gradually added to the solution while heating on water bath and finally the mixture was heated for one hour on the water bath. It was centrifuged and the centrifugate was dissolved by adding sodium hydroxide solution (pH 9.0). The humic acid material was precipitated at pH 2-3 by adding 0.1 N HCl. The subsequent process of purification is the same as in the case GL-H except that before dialysis the material was washed several times with ether in order to remove any adsorbed monomer. CA-H was prepared by air oxidation instead of by persulphate. It was purified as above.

Hydroquinone Humic Acid (HQ-H): It was prepared and purified in the same way as CT-H taking hydroquinone (1.6 gm) and sixteen different amino acids (each 0.1 gm).

Electrometric Titration :

The continuous titration with NaOH was done at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$, with the help of a Leeds-Northrup conductivity bridge using 1000 cycle oscillator and a conductivity cell having a low cell constant. The titrations are shown in Fig. 1. Both continuous and discontinuous potentiometric measurements in presence as well as in absence of neutral salts were

end points have been located in the usual manner by drawing the differential curves (not shown).

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titration curves of catechol humic acid
O, Discontinuous titration; □, Continuous titration;
●, Continuous (in 0.1M KCl) titration.

Fig. 1. Conductometric titration curves.
Catechol humic acid (O), Hydroquinone humic acid (Δ),
Glucose humic acid (\square).

carried out with the help of a Cambridge Bench type pH meter. The glass electrode was checked with buffer solutions at pH 4.0, 6.98 and 9.18. The titration curves are shown in Figs. 2, 3 & 4. The

Results and Discussion

The conductometric curves show a single break indicating a monobasic character of these humic acids

Fig. 3. Potentiometric titration curves of hydroquinone humic acid O, Discontinuous titration; Δ , Continuous titration \bullet , Continuous titration (in 0.1M KCl)

Fig. 4. Potentiometric titration curves of glucose humic acid. O, Discontinuous titration; Δ , Continuous titration; \square , Continuous (in 0.1M KCl) titration.

and in general the features of weak acids, similar to those observed by Van Dijk¹ with synthetic as well as natural humic acids.

The initial conductances at the same concentration of the humic acids (Table 1) can be arranged in the order :

The initial pH's at the same concentration (Table 3) are in the reverse order. The initial conductances can also be calculated from initial pH values assuming that H^+ ions alone contribute to the conductance. The values so calculated compare well with the observed ones (Table 1). The b.e.c.'s of different humic acid preparations are relatively low (340-346 m.e./100 gm) compared to those usually observed with soil humic acids¹⁸ (300-700 m.e./100 gm). The specific conductances at the equivalence points (i.e., of the sodium humate solution) vary from 17.0 to $24.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ at 30° the corresponding values for soil humic acid¹⁶ being of the same order, viz., 25.0 to $37.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ at 30°.

TABLE 1

System	Concentration %	Specific conductance at		
		$\alpha_n = 0 \times 10^5$ (obs.)	$\alpha_n = 0 \times 10^5$ (calc.)	$\alpha_n = 1 \times 10^5$ (obs.)
HQ-H	0.045	3.86	2.19	24.0
CT-H	0.045	4.08	2.35	19.0
CA-H	0.045	5.04	4.69	—
GL-H	0.045	3.15	1.39	17.0

The discontinuous titrations yield in general higher values of b.e.c. than those by continuous titrations, probably as the result of a more prolonged reaction. Like soil humic acids the total acidity values of synthetic humic acids as reflected in their equivalent weights (Table 2) are less by potentiometric than by conductometric method. The synthetic humic acids also have remarkable buffer capacities in the pH range 3.5 to 7.0.

TABLE 2

System	Equivalent weights (potentiometric method)		Equivalent weights (conductometric method)
	Continuous titration	Discontinuous titration	Continuous titration
HQ-H	424	413	281
CT-H	403	400	294
GL-H	476	490	417

The apparent pK_{av} values as determined from half-neutralisation point of potentiometric titration curves range from 6.85 to 7.25. If these humic acid preparations are not treated as very weak acids, an approximate pK_{av} can be obtained from the equation: $\text{pH} = \frac{1}{2}\text{pK}_{av} - \frac{1}{2} \log C$, by plotting pH against $-\log C$ (Fig. 5C) and finding out the pH corresponding to $-\log C = 0$. These values given in Table 3 range from 6.7 to 7.2 and compare well with the values from pH titration curves.

The addition of salt (0.1 M KCl) lowers the pK_{av} value by about 1.0 to 1.4 units (cf. Table 3). The reported pK_{av} -values for soil humic acid¹⁹ ranging

TABLE 3

System (Conc. 0.045%)	Initial pH (obs)	pK _{av} (from the graph)			pK _{int}		pH at the equiv. point •	
		pH vs. -log C graph	Dis- continuous titration	Continuous titration	Dis- continuous titration	Continuous titration	Dis- continuous titration (in 0.1 M KCl)	Continuous titration
HQ-H	4.25	7.2	7.05	7.02	6.05	—	7.55	8.00
„ +0.1M KCl	3.98	—	—	5.65	—	4.99	—	7.85
CT-H	4.22	6.9	7.2	7.0	5.98	—	7.85	8.15
„ +0.1M KCl	3.75	—	—	5.6	—	4.95	—	7.25
GL-H	4.45	6.7	7.25	6.85	5.57	—	8.52	8.12
„ +0.1M KCl	3.86	—	—	5.85	—	4.87	—	8.00
CA-H	3.92	6.2	—	—	—	—	—	—
„ +0.1M KCl	3.64	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

from 5.4 to 6.4 are lower, while those of Merck's humic acid²⁰ ranging from 6.8 to 7.0 are in good agreement with the values presented here. It ought to be noted that in this calculation of pK_{av}, the assumption of one kind of dissociable group in the molecule is more or less inherent. This, as we know, is hardly the case in the case of natural as well as synthetic humic acids.

Regarding the dependence of $\left(\log \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} - \text{pH}\right)$ on α (where α is the degree of dissociation of the polyion at any stage during neutralisation), Figs. 5(a) & 5(b)

Fig. 5a. ●, Catechol humic acid; O, Hyd. humic acid, Δ, Glucose humic acid (from discontinuous titration curve).

Fig. 5b Δ, Glucose humic acid (in 0.1M KCl); O, Hydroquinone humic acid (in 0.1M KCl); ●, Catechol humic acid (in 0.1M KCl).

show that the relevant curves are linear in presence of 0.1 M KCl but are not so in its absence. The

Fig. 5c. ●, Glucose humic acid; O, Hyd. humic acid; Δ, Catechol humic acid (by S₂O₈²⁻); □, Catechol humic acid (By O₂).

non-linear nature would mean, following Tanford's argument²¹, that the electrostatic free energy of dissociation and hence the size of the molecule change with ionization. This is in accord with expectations since these synthetic humic acids are polyelectrolytes as revealed by their viscosity properties²² and they obviously do expand with increasing charge. In presence of 0.1 M KCl, however, the polyelectrolytic behaviour is suppressed and hence linearity of the curves (Fig. 5c) is observed.

The values of pK_{int} (obtained from the extrapolation of the straight line $(\text{pH} - \log \alpha / 1 - \alpha \text{ vs. } \alpha)$ plots of Figs. 5a and 5b) for synthetic humic acids in absence of electrolytes are quite high (5.57-6.05) in comparison to 4.7 for side chain carboxyl groups in polyacids. This discrepancy may arise from the fact that the assumption of a single type of dissociable group is probably not correct. The participation of, for instance, a large number of phenolic groups will obviously cause a greater value in pK_{int}. In a macromolecule having different kinds of titratable groups, the pK_{int} for each kind can be evaluated separately, if the number of each type is known.

It is to be noted from the results given in Table 3 that when salt is added the values of pK_{int} are lowered and become closer (4.87-4.99) to the actual value, viz., 4.7 for the carboxyls. In presence of salts the polyelectrolyte molecules become coiled and compact, and perhaps most of the phenolic groups get buried in the coil of the molecule. Moreover, in presence of electrolytes the exposed phenolic hydroxyls undergo exchange reactions, viz., $-OH + K^+ = O-K^+ + H^+$, which is corroborated by the observed pH drop in 0.1 M KCl (Table 3) initial pH 's). This is equivalent to a lowering of pK_{int} for those phenolic groups. Both these factors, in different degrees, are probably responsible for the lowering of pK_{int} in presence of salts.

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